

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones : Part—IV

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Manuscript received 2 November 1977, revised 15 March 1978, accepted 3 April 1978

Thermal condensation of 2-methylresorcinol with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate gave 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ia), which on allylation followed by Claisen rearrangement gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ic). (Ic) was converted to 9-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one(IIa) by treatment with osmium tetroxide followed by polyphosphoric acid. (IIb) was obtained by treating (Ic) with conc. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal(10%).

In recent years furochromones have received considerable attention as they not only occur in nature but also possess therapeutic properties. It was, therefore, thought of interest to synthesise Khellin¹ and Visnagin² type of compounds which are likely to be physiologically active.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of furochromones³, we report here the synthesis of 9-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)-benzopyran-4-one(IIa), 7,9-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)-benzopyran-4-one(IIb). Condensation of 2-methylresorcinol with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate in refluxing diphenyl ether according to Desai, Trivedi and Sethna⁴ gave 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ia). This on allylation with allyl bromide afforded the corresponding 7-allyl ether derivative(Ib) which was subjected to Claisen rearrangement to give 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ic). (Ic) on treatment with osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate⁵ in ethyl acetate, afforded 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-6-acetaldehyde-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Id). Cyclisation of (Id) with polyphosphoric acid gave 9-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one(IIa).

Cyclisation of (Ic) by trituration with conc. sulphuric acid according to Shaikh and Trivedi⁶ afforded 7,9-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydrocyclo-

(I)

- (Ia) R = -CH₃, R₁ = -OH, R₂ = H
 (Ib) R = -CH₃, R₁ = -OCH₂CH=CH₂, R₂ = H
 (Ic) R = -CH₃, R₁ = -OH, R₂ = -CH₂CH=CH₂
 (Id) R = -CH₃, R₁ = -OH, R₂ = -CH₂CHO

(II)

- (IIa) R = -CH₃, R₁ = H
 (IIb) R = R₁ = -CH₃

(III)

penta(b)furo(3, 2-g)-benzopyran-4-one(III). Dehydrogenation of (III) with palladised charcoal in boiling diphenyl ether furnished 7,9-dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3, 2-g)benzopyran-4-one(IIb).

Experimental

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ia) :

A mixture of 2-methylresorcinol (3 g) and ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (4 ml) was refluxed with diphenylether (10 ml) for three hours with a short condenser to facilitate the removal of alcohol formed. After cooling the separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from dimethyl formamide. m.p. 309°, yield 2 g. (Found : C, 71.54 ; H, 5.47 ; C₁₈H₂₂O₃ requires C, 72.21 ; H, 5.55%).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ib) :

A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (2 g) allyl bromide

(1.2 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g) was refluxed in dry dimethyl formamide (150 ml) in a water bath for 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into water. The separated product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound and crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 137°, yield 1.3 g. (Found : C, 74.86 ; H, 5.95 ; $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ic) :

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (2 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (10 ml) for 8 hrs., after cooling the reaction mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml) containing pieces of ice. The separated product was filtered and dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was filtered. The filtrate on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid gave the product which was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 222°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 74.74 ; H, 6.28 ; $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%). IR spectrum (nujol) 1635 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl>C=O group) and a broad band at 3300 cm^{-1} (aromatic hydroxy group).

6-Acetaldehyde-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one(Ia) :

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (500 mg) dissolved in ethyl acetate (100 ml) was vigorously shaken with osmium tetroxide (50 mg) and water (100 ml). To the dark solution was added potassium periodate (2 g in 0 ml water) dropwise over a period of 3 hrs. The ethyl acetate layer was separated, dried and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in chloroform and the clear solution was percolated through a short column of alumina. The residue left after evaporation of chloroform crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 260° (decomp.), yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 69.76 ; H, 5.51 ; $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.69 ; H, 5.42%).

9-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one(IIa) :

6-Acetaldehyde-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (250 mg) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 ml) in a water bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr., and then poured into ice water. The solid separated was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. A chloroform extract of the dried residue was passed over a short column of alumina. Evaporation of solvent left a product which crystallised from benzene, m.p. 266°, yield 100 mg. (Found : C, 74.84 ; H, 5.01 ; $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 5.00%). IR spectrum (nujol) 875 cm^{-1} (furan ring), 1615 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl>C=O group). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{chloroform}}$ 245 nm (log e 4.76), 278 nm (log e 4.17), 314 nm (log e 3.99).

7,9-Dimethyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7-hexahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one(III) :

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)benzopyran-4-one (1 g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) in a water bath for 10 min. The content were poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 154°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 75.01 ; H, 6.45 ; $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%). IR spectrum (nujol) 1630 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl>C=O group). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{methanol}}$ 249 nm (log e 4.18) 300 nm (log e 4.18).

7,9-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one(IIb) :

A mixture of 7,9-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydrocyclopenta(b)furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-4-one (0.5 g) and palladised charcoal (10% ; 0.3 g) and diphenyl ether (4 ml) was refluxed for 10 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and petroleum ether was added to the cooled filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. The product was purified by passing its benzene solution over a short column of alumina. Evaporation of solvent left a product which crystallised from benzene, m.p. 212°, yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 76.17 ; H, 5.53 ; $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.00 ; H, 5.51%). IR spectrum (nujol) 835 cm^{-1} (furan ring), 1630 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl>C=O group). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{methanol}}$ 246 nm (log e 4.82), 290 nm (log e 4.19), 298 nm (log e 4.11), 320 nm (log e 4.03).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. S. M. Sethna, Pro-Vice Chancellor of M. S. University of Baroda for his keen interest in the work, Dr. S. S. Lele and Shri S. S. Madhav Rao for the micro analysis of the compounds.

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